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The Use of Coaching In the Australian Rail Industry

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Abstract

The purpose of the research reported in this paper is to investigate ways to build and promote the internal coaching capacity within Australia's rail industry. The research has utilized a mixed methods research design across two sequential phases. This paper reports on the results from the first phase, which employed an online survey of Australian rail organisations. The findings indicate a high level of internal coaching activity exists informally across the Australian rail industry. Engagement in the coaching process by both coach and coachee was also perceived as the most important factor in relation to increasing the effectiveness of coaching activities.

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1. Introduction

In recent years coaching has become one of the major growth industries (Skiffington and Zeuss, 2001) and a survey conducted by the Chartered Institute of Professional Development, revealed that four fifths of the 500 companies surveyed claimed to use coaching in their organization (CIPD, 2004).

There are several commonly used definitions of coaching which is a term derived from the Anglo-Saxon word meaning carriage. This word means to take a person from where they are now to where they want to be. Ebrahimi and Cameron (2012) in their discussion on internal coaching compiled a Table of commonly used definitions of coaching as displayed in Table 1.

An extensive literature review on contemporary coaching research and practices has been conducted and as a result the research questions which have been posited for this study are as follows

RQ1: How is internal coaching differentiated from external coaching?

RQ2: What are the characteristics of an effective internal coaching program?

RQ3: What knowledge, skills and attributes (KSAs) are needed to be an effective internal coach?

Table 1. Definitions of Coaching

Source	Definition
Passmore & Fillery-Travis (2011, p.74)	'A Socratic based dialogue between a facilitator (coach) and a participant (client) where the majority of interventions used by the facilitator are open questions which are aimed at stimulating the self-awareness and personal responsibility of the participant'
Peterson & Hicks (1996, p.14)	'Coaching is the process of equipping people with the tools, knowledge, and opportunities they need to develop themselves and become more effective'
Homan & Miller (2008, p.7)	'Coaching is a deliberate process using focused conversations to create an environment for individual growth, purposeful action, and sustained improvement'
Clutterbuck (1998, p.19)	'Coaching is a pragmatic approach to helping people manage their acquisition or improvement of skills'

Source: Ebrahimi and Cameron (2012, p.5)

The research has employed a mixed methods research design with two sequential phases. The first phase involved a quantitative survey of rail organisations and was followed by in depth case studies of two rail organisations. As noted by Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2009, p.265) 'in general, mixed methods research represents research that involves collecting, analysing, and interpreting quantitative and qualitative data in a single study or in a series of studies that investigate the same underlying phenomenon'.

The paper presents data relevant to coaching from the quantitative phase of the research. This data is derived from an online survey of Australian rail organisations which achieved a response rate of 50.3% (n=65). Rail organisations were asked a series of questions related to their use and intended use of coaching within their respective organisations. Firstly we discuss internal and external coaching before presenting the study's methodology and findings from the quantitative online survey administered in the first phase of the study. The findings that focus on the perceived benefits of coaching and the importance of coach-coachee relationship specifically in internal coaching programs, and conclusions is presented.

2. Literature Review

In the context of management, coaching is known as a popular tool which is used in organisational development strategy and assists employees address individual functional knowledge gaps and skills (Ladyshevsky, 2010; Joo, 2005; Yu, 2007). The manager as a coach role is defined as 'a process where managers create opportunities for an individual to gain insights into their performance, aimed at guiding and inspiring employees to improve their work' (Ladyshevsky, 2010, p.293). McLean et al. (2005) highlights the fact that the concept of manager as a coach has been developed in the literature since 1980s, and can be considered as a strategy to change the relationship between a boss and his or her employee.

There can also some challenges and complications in this type of in-house coaching where the manager plays the role of an internal coach. For example, finding the time to coach can be a challenge for many managers (Goleman, 2000; Goleman et al., 2002). This can be particularly more complicated for managers who have a large number of direct reports. In this case, the available time of the internal coaches can be limited based on their workload and the given multiple demand. Furthermore, Orth et al. (1987, p.67) explains that time, training, changes in attitudes, and sometimes frustrating practice are needed to develop coaching skills and to incorporate these skills into a person's management style.

In the manager as a coach form of in-house coaching, the outcomes of coaching interventions are also critically dependent on the manager's emotional intelligence. Coaching is a psychological interpersonal process, and the role of emotions and how these are leveraged is critical to learning and development in a coaching relationship (Goleman et al., 2002). 'Those who can manage the competencies of self awareness, self management, social awareness and relationship management, have consistently been found to be high performers and are able to use these skills to enhance others' human performance' (Ladyshefsky, 2010, p.294).

There are some key differences between internal and external coaching. Despite the fact that external coaching can be a costly option for organizations and the cost of external coaches may vary 'from \$10,000 to \$100,000 per person' (Rock and Donde, 2008, p.11), there is still some evidence that confirms external coaching has its advantages and benefits: An outside coach allows staff to be more open and candid about their goals and concerns. Some employees may feel misgivings and mistrust about revealing dissatisfaction about their careers to managers. External coaches may be perceived as being less biased and more empathic (Whitmore, 2002).

Frisch (2001, p.243) asserts 'internal coaches can often use their existing insight about the organization and its players to make faster initial progress in suggestion a development agenda'. Furthermore, leaders, managers and HR personnel may be more familiar with the company's culture and climate than external coaches, as they are integrated into the organization, more aware of future directions and the projected required skills and competencies the organization is seeking (Whitmore 2002).

3. Methodology

The study utilised a mixed methods research (MMR) approach through the application of an exploratory mixed methods research (MMR) design. This MMR design has been identified as 'a two phased approach' (Creswell and Plano Clark 2007, p.77). The design begins with qualitative data collection to explore a phenomenon followed by a quantitative phase as shown in Figure III. As a deviation to this design, the first phase will be quantitative followed by a qualitative phase. The quantitative data was collected through an online survey of the Australian rail industry to gauge the current and intended coaching activity across the industry. This has been followed by a case study approach, which will be used to build on the results of the first quantitative phase.

Figure 1: Exploratory Mixed Methods Research Design

In depth case studies are currently being conducted with two large rail industry organizations. One in Queensland (QLD), and the other in New South Wales (NSW). The results of the online survey has informed the data collection in the case studies, as both these organisations are large and relatively well resourced in terms of learning and development funds with both having begun developing and implementing coaching programs.

The online survey instrument was designed and developed through a comprehensive literature review, a comparative analysis of an online coaching survey conducted in the UK (CIPD 2006) and through consultation with the Project Steering Committee which is made up of the university based researchers and rail organisation representatives. The Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD) conducted an Annual Learning and Development Survey in 2006. The survey found that 'a coaching culture is considered 'very important' or 'important' to the success of an organisation by 93% of the respondents who undertake coaching activities (CIPD 2006, p.2). The online survey for this research was administered through the membership of the Australasian Railway Association (ARA) membership and utilised SurveyMonkey software. Each member of this employer association has a 'point of contact' for the ARA and the survey was emailed to 129 rail organisations through their respective points of contact. The survey was open for a two week period in August 2012, with one reminder being sent after the first week. Sixty-four rail organisations responded which equated to a response rate of 50.3%. The survey contained 28 questions of these 12 were forced choice single response, 12 were forced choice multiple response, 3 contained rating scales and 1 was open ended.

4. Findings

The focus of the data presented for this paper will be on the perceived purposes and uses of caching, and the key factors involved to increase coach-coachee engagement in coaching programs. Figure 2 provides a graph depicting the responses to Question 25 of the survey which asked respondents to choose from 14 options when answering the question "Generally speaking, when do you think that coaching works? The top response for this question was: "When there is engagement in the process by both the coach and coachee".

Figure 2: When coaching works

5. Discussion

Responses in Figure 2 demonstrate how important the engagement of the coach and coachee is in the coaching program. The strategy that the research suggests to increase the engagement factor, in particular in internal coaching interventions, is to focus on relationship conditions and to increase the mutual trust and the mutual security to develop open and honest dialogue between the coach and the coachee.

Findings from the research indicate that, successful internal coaching interventions in the workplace require a high level of engagement from both internal coach and the coachee in the coaching process. On the other hand, some scholars claim that, the increased level of trust in a coaching program, can change the climate towards a more positive and effective coaching environment (Evans, 2011; Massey and Kyngdon, 2005; McAllister, 1995; Hurley 2006). The importance of trust in building long term and effective coaching relationship is more critical in an internal coaching program. The reason being that 'with an external coach the client can assume a level of organizational detachment, whereas with an internal coach both coach and client are likely to continue working in the same organization long after the coaching program has completed' (Machine 2010, p.43).

Challenges of coaching in the workplace may include the complexity of building trust between the coach and the coachee where the manager coaches his or her direct reports. This may lead to a lack of engagement in coaching sessions by the coachee, and therefore some unreliable and uncertain outcomes followed by further conflict, confusion and distrust at work. Building a high level of trust between the in-house coach and the coachee becomes more difficult if 'the coach has a stake in the coachee's future at work' (Wilson 2011, p.413). Furthermore, the study has also demonstrated consistency with Scoular's (2009, p.96) findings that 'willingness and good chemistry were by far the most frequently cited ingredients of a successful coaching relationship'.

6. Conclusion

Coaching has been identified by the Australian rail industry as an important strategy for workforce development. The purpose of the research is to investigate ways to build and promote the internal coaching capacity within Australia's rail industry. This study has conducted a quantitative online survey of rail organisations in Australia to determine the use of coaching within the Australian rail industry. A response rate of 50.3% was achieved for the survey which has provided a broad brush scan of coaching activities across Australia's rail organizations. The paper has focused on the use of internal coaches and the creation of a coaching culture before taking note of the findings in respect to key components of the coaching relationship. Engagement in the coaching process and the nature of the coaching relationship were found to be of high importance to the success of a coaching program or activity. The research points to two key aspects of the coaching relationship in respect to this engagement and perceived success: trust and willingness. Although the research is limited to the Australian rail industry the findings have implications for organizations across the globe, especially those wishing to invest in a comprehensive coaching programme whether this is using internal coaches, external coaches or a combination of both. The investment in a coaching program can be substantial and a well informed approach to its instigation and development will ensure greater returns on investment.

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